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The creation of a citizen observatory campaign aimed at promoting cycling through FLAMENCO: an open and reconfigurable digital platform

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Abstract

Recently there has been an increasing tendency towards bottom-up travel surveys when stakeholders initiate data collection campaigns in citizen observatories. This way, citizens can observe our environment by collecting data using smartphones. However, deploying new citizen observatories remains technically difficult and labor-intensive. The Flanders Mobile Enacted Citizen Observatories project (FLAMENCO) has developed an open, reusable and reconfigurable citizen observatory platform which allows ICT-agnostic stakeholders to initiate new citizen observatories. Recently, a first campaign has been created through the platform with the aim of motivating students to cycle. In this paper we validate a technical framework under real life conditions, we examine the guidance needed when creating a citizen observatory and we evaluate whether the citizen observatory gives the desired results in terms of accuracy and user experience. The results of creating and evaluating the use case serves as a basis for a comprehensive manual that will later be developed.

Keywords: Citizen observatories; participatory sensing; technical requirements; travel surveys; data collection

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1. Introduction

Transition to smartphone-based travel surveys is becoming essential, as older survey methods such as telephone landline surveys have encountered several issues. Besides the declining number of respondents, traditional travel survey methods face incomplete and inaccurate data collection (Barbeau, Labrador, Georggi, Winters, & Perez, 2008), rising survey costs (Inbakaran & Kroen, 2011; Jariyasunant et al., 2011), and retrospective data collection which imposes a heavy burden on respondents (Gonzalez et al., 2010; Greene, Flake, Hathaway, & Geilich, 2016; Hamid Safi, Assemi, Mesbah, Ferreira, & Hickman, 2015). With the continuous improvement of sensors and data processing abilities, smartphones have been proven to be a valuable tool for mobility-related research. The smartphone is a useful intermediary to provide campaign organizers with qualitative and quantitative data such as routes, travel times, speed, etc. Connected devices can collect quantitative data about mobility, as well as qualitative information that might be used to gain better insight into the trip context. Together with this transition, there has been an increasing tendency towards bottom-up initiatives where citizens themselves initiate data collection campaigns in citizen observatories (Liu, Grossberndt, & Kobernus, 2017). In citizen observatories, sensor data is being collected, analyzed and visualized by volunteers with the help of ICT-tools, to improve the citizens' quality of life. But deploying a new citizen observatory requires specific knowledge of organizing a campaign and is often labor-intensive and expensive, which acts as a significant barrier to their deployment.

The Flanders Mobile Enacted Citizen Observatories project (FLAMENCO) has developed an open, reusable and reconfigurable citizen observatory platform which allows ICT-agnostic stakeholders to initiate new citizen observatories in various domains such as mobility and environment. This facilitates citizens to be more engaged in observing our environment by collecting data using smart mobile devices to support decision making. This platform combines two of Haklay's (2017) six types of citizen science: participatory sensing and civic science. Whereas the former gives participants control over the process and involves them actively in selecting data that will be collected and analyzed, the latter has a bottom-up approach that allows participants to propose and steer the campaign in order to address specific concerns (Keseru, Wuytens, & Macharis, 2018).

To create such a platform, technical standards that are valid for mobility related citizen observatories need to be set. In addition, we need to define general guidelines for creating citizen observatories and for evaluating them. This way, ICT agnostic stakeholders are empowered to create a citizen observatory themselves. Current literature states that more research is needed to define standards applied to smartphone data collection in transport, due to the diversity in objectives, applied methods and sample characteristics (Harding, 2017; Prelipcean, Gidófalvi, & Susilo, 2016). As part of the FLAMENCO project we aim to draw up technical requirements for a citizen observatory that collects data on travel behavior. Based on previous experience with smartphone-based travel surveys from literature we build a theoretical framework that could serve as a standard for technical requirements in mobility related citizen observatories.

However, citizen observatories are versatile and often have different requirements related to data collection, processing, feedback and visualization, validation and overall complexity. Therefore, technical requirements based only on scientific literature do not suffice and should be complemented with real experiences. In the spring of 2019, a first citizen observatory campaign was created through the platform, which allows us to validate the theoretically drawn up technical framework under real life conditions. The citizen observatory is aimed at tracking the cycling routes of Flemish university students. The objective of the campaign is to map the most popular routes to school as well as potential issues along certain routes. This paper aims at improving the FLAMENCO platform by monitoring a real-life use case. The results will lead to concrete steps/measures that are needed to create standards concerning the creation, technical requirements and evaluation of citizen observatories aiming to collect data on travel behavior. We have defined three research questions:

1. How does the theoretically drawn up technical framework of FLAMENCO correspond to a realistic use case?
2. How much guidance is needed when creating a citizen observatory through the FLAMENCO platform?
3. Does the citizen observatory, created by the FLAMENCO platform, give adequate results in terms of accuracy and user experience?

To answer the research questions, we start this paper with a theoretical framework based on scientific literature on smartphone travel surveys from the last decade. In a following section we convert theory into practice by creating a real-life use case together with the campaign organizer Trein Tram Bus. We do this in four steps: first, we set requirements with the help of interviews and a guided document. Secondly, we co-create the campaign in an interdisciplinary workshop. In a third step the actual campaign is tested and lastly, we evaluate the results. The paper ends with a conclusion.

2. Theoretical framework

The theoretical framework aims to study the technical requirements for organising successful citizen observatories for mobility. Based on the existing literature we draw up preliminary guidelines for organising data collection campaigns focusing on mobility-related data. The guidelines provide recommendations concerning data collection, processing, feedback, validation, user interaction, and acceptance. The literature review focuses on the registration of trips and trip characteristics for travel behaviour analysis, locational data collection as well as quantifiable measures and requirements.

This chapter consists of a review of scientific literature regarding smartphone-based travel surveys, showing their evolution of the last decade. Based on the best practices in the reviewed literature, we develop parameter-specific guidelines required for data collection. With this, we further explain the role that the Flamenco platform can play in this novel data collection method.

2.1. Review of smartphone-based travel surveys

While GPS-based travel surveys have been used since the 1990s, smartphone-based travel survey applications have only been on the rise for the past years. We examined 14 examples, dating from 2005 to 2016, and mention the most important ones with their most relevant results. It should be mentioned that smartphone travel surveys do also have downsides compared to traditional travel surveys. Signal loss, high energy consumption, forgetting to bring the smartphone, or not having access to a smartphone reduce the accuracy and representativeness of the collected data (Abdulazim, Abdelgawad, Habib, & Abdulhai, 2013; Nitsche, Widhalm, Breuss, Brändle, & Maurer, 2014).

One of the first smartphone surveys was executed by Ohmori, Nakazato, & Harata (2005) who experimented with two-types of data collection: a smartphone GPS and paper-and-pen, to establish an automated travel diary. The conclusions drawn from the experiment were that the smartphone data set reduced the data handling time of the surveyor compared to the data set of the paper-and-pen survey. Moreover, the smartphone data entry frequency was higher than the traditional survey method, there was a high level of battery depletion and participants' burden depended largely on their personal characteristics. TRACT-IT, a software application developed by Barbeau et al. (2008), supported travel surveys with providing real-time commuter data. The application suffered from technical difficulties such as lack of GPS recording, which made the usefulness of the data very limited. Therefore, with the advancement of GPS technology and the emergence of additional sensors in smartphones the detection of travel mode became more and more a research priority. In 2011, an experiment in San Francisco (Jariyasunant et al., 2011) had participants collect location data through their own smartphone and combined this data with third-party data from transit agencies, to calculate more useful output. The data collection period was preceded by an attitudinal survey and after the data collection period the participants had to fill in another survey to assess their changes in travel behavior. To compare the feasibility of smartphone-based surveys with traditional travel surveys, Nitsche, Widhalm, Breuss, & Maurer (2012) explained the requirements to set up a travel survey and listed the constraints and limitations of a smartphone-based survey: the survey is required to be representative, comparable and precise. Participant's acceptance and data protection is required, and the technical requirements of the data collection devices need to be determined beforehand.

In the following years, more sophisticated smartphone-based travel survey applications have been assessed and improved, such as the Quantified Traveller System (Jariyasunant et al., 2012), UbiActive (Fan, Chen, Liao, & Douma, 2012), FMS in Singapore (Pereira et al., 2013), iDiary (Feldman, Sugaya, Sung, & Rus, 2013), ATLAS and ATLAS II (Hamid Safi et al., 2015), Sydney Travel & Health Survey (Greaves et al., 2015), rMove (Greene et al., 2016) and MEILI, an open source travel diary collection system that can process raw GPS data into trip and trip leg identification and mode detection (Prelicean, Susilo, & Gidófalvi, 2017).

2.2. Guidelines for technical requirements for mobility campaigns

Based on the consulted literature, we have developed a theoretical framework for the technical requirements to organize successful data collection campaigns. This framework is illustrated in figure 1 and consists of three main stages: First, the raw data needs to be collected. Secondly, this data needs to be processed into valuable behavioral and environmental information. Lastly, this information needs to be reported back to all stakeholders in the form of clear feedback. Throughout the entire lifespan of the campaign, the collected information needs to be validated and user acceptance needs to be ensured by motivating (maintain the interest in using the application) and interacting with the participants.

Fig. 1 Framework for the technical requirements to organize a data collection campaign in the mobility domain

2.2.1. Data collection

When deploying a citizen observatory campaign, raw data needs to be collected before it becomes information. Some data such as speed, time and used travel mode can be collected automatically, and other data, for example socio-demographic data, requires active input from the participant and, if necessary, should be collected via an intake survey. It is important to mention that data collected using smartphone-based travel surveys can never be 100% representative. Nevertheless, it is of crucial importance to have a high level of representativeness. Before deploying a smartphone-based travel survey, the campaign organizer needs to define three main constraints, namely the location constraint (geographical zone), time constraint (period of data collection) and population constraint (specific group from which the data will be collected). During the data collection, specific attention should be paid for spatial distribution (of trips and respondents), temporal distribution, socio-demographic representativeness (at least age and gender), modal distribution of trips, distribution of trips by travel purpose (Nitsche et al., 2012) and other specific characteristics such as car ownership. To increase representativeness, one needs participants. Therefore, data collection activities with low barriers need to be created, as well as incentives, in a transparent matter where participants feel respected (See et al., 2017).

Data can automatically be collected by different smartphone sensors, of which the GPS and accelerometer sensors are used most often. The GPS sensor collects the most accurate and complete data but comes with the cost of a high battery drain and is therefore not advised to be used on its own. The cellular network, wi-fi and magnetic sensor (compass) are advised to only be used complementary to (one of) the two first sensors. The technical requirements of the devices themselves are also an important indicator of the data accuracy. When transferring the data to the servers, campaign organizers need to make a choice between uploading via the cellular network (which can come with a financial cost) or through a wi-fi connection (which will probably not always be sent in real-time). The choice should be based on the specific needs of the campaign, e.g. if real-time data transfer needed or not.

2.2.2. Data processing

Raw data needs to be processed to extract meaningful information, such as the detection of certain travel modes and trip attributes. Prior to any processing at the trip level, it is common to detect trips and to segment these trips into trip legs (Prelicean et al., 2016). Furthermore, the collected data needs to be cleaned since GPS data is frequently noisy. This can be done, for example, with a Kalman (1960) filter that uses GPS data, cell location data and predictions to compute an accurate and smooth trajectory (Nitsche et al., 2014).

Similar to the use of the GPS sensor, when it comes to data processing it is again important to make a trade-off between accuracy and battery drain according to the needs of the campaign: although it is possible to reach a 100% accuracy in identifying trip legs (Shin et al., 2015; Tsui & Shalaby, 2006), a high accuracy may come with a faster battery depletion.

When trips are separated into trip legs, we can identify the transport mode of each trip leg. The distinction between standing still, walking and other transport modes can be made with a 100% accuracy by using sensor data alone (Harding, 2017; Prelicean et al., 2016). When involving other modes, the accuracy will drop significantly using smartphone sensors. To overcome the limitations of automatic mode detection, the transport mode identified by the software can be validated by the participant (Cottrill et al., 2013). When considering this, one should consider that the respondent burden needs to be as low as possible to achieve high quality data. Before deploying a campaign, the organizers need to consider which transport modes are of their primary interest and select the appropriate campaign design to meet their needs.

Since most trips have a purpose at the destination, transport planning also requires information about activities at the origin and destination of trips. Trip purpose might be derived from the end destination, but techniques such as automatic detection of destination, machine learning and integration of third-party point of interest (POI) databases such as Yelp are not fully developed yet (Cottrill et al., 2013; Feldman et al., 2013). Due to these technical limitations, trip purpose should only be received by requesting user input, unless the travel destinations that are of interest for a campaign are trips to school or work, which are easily definable. Additional trip attributes that require direct user input (for which in-app prompts should be included) include vehicle occupancy, type of vehicle, travel cost (Greene et al., 2016), pick-up and drop-off behavior and trip satisfaction (Raveau et al., 2016).

2.2.3. Feedback to participants and campaign organizers

More than passive data collection, citizen observatories should actively motivate data collectors by providing feedback to participants, campaign organizers and other stakeholders (Liu et al., 2017). The feedback-function is one of the main differences that distinguishes citizen observatories from 'regular' smartphone-based travel surveys. Through fixed algorithms, the data should be processed to high quality indicators that translate into easily interpretable visualizations about travel routes, such as spreadsheets, heat maps and isochronal maps (Bossuyt, Christiaens, Deham, Franchois, & Vleugels, 2016). Three types of feedback carriers should be considered in the citizen observatory: in-app visualizations for participants, an online dashboard displaying additional feedback for participants and an administrator website for campaign organizers, which should include possibilities for advanced analytics, data export and campaign management functions. Whereas due to its digital nature, the platform can only present the collected data in a digital format, the campaign organizers can further distribute these results among participants and other stakeholders (e.g. policy makers) in non-digital formats such as newsletters, leaflets, workshops and events.

The following indicators should be calculated automatically to create meaningful feedback to users and policy makers: travel time by mode, travel distance by mode, average speed by mode, arrival and departure times, location of trip origins and destinations, travel route, CO₂ emissions, health impact (e.g. calories burnt), external cost, and average travel cost.

2.2.4. Validation

The participatory data, obtained by smartphone-sensors and fixed algorithms, needs to be validated by the user to improve accuracy and make evaluation possible by obtaining ground truth data. This validation can occur at any point when data is collected and/or processed. However, the campaign organizers need to bear in mind the trade-off between user burden and data accuracy. To eliminate user burden, the process of validation should be simplified

as much as possible. Once an algorithm is validated and an acceptable success rate is reached, additional burden of user interaction (see for example Greene et al. (2016); Safi et al., (2015)) should be avoided. To reduce user burden, different strategies should be considered. The reviewed literature provides three main options of data validation. A first option is to ask for real-time validation when needed, through prompted recall interaction. The two other options both concern retrospective validation, namely through diary validation at the end of a fixed period (e.g. once a day) and after the campaign. Each option has their own benefits and limitations. Campaign organizers should therefore pick the validation options depending on the objectives of the campaigns and how the data will be used.

2.2.5. User interaction, acceptance and motivation

As mentioned earlier, citizen observatories are user-centric by nature and should ensure user-friendliness and minimize burden. An easy-to-use and motivating campaign encourages participation, which is a common challenge of participatory sensing. An important indicator to evaluate the usability of the software is the proportion of users finishing the data collection campaign without additional support requests (Hamid Safi et al., 2015). Gamification and the provision of auxiliary functions (such as personal information about travel behavior) can incentivize participants and increase the number of participants finishing the campaign. An exit survey can also provide information about the survey experience and any additional information about extraordinary behavior during the survey period. Lastly, it should be ensured that participants participate voluntarily in the data collection and are made aware on the relevant privacy policies associated with the campaigns (Nitsche et al., 2012).

3. Method

After developing a theoretical framework and setting up technical requirements for the FLAMENCO citizen observatory platform, we validate this framework under real life conditions. The requirements described in the previous chapter reflect a ‘best-case scenario’ that will further be analysed in a first use case, created together with non-profit organisation Trein Tram Bus (TTB). The use case has been co-created and afterwards evaluated with the campaign organiser and campaign participants. Whereas the knowledge creation in this use case was through an organisation that represents citizens, a next phase in the research would be to let citizen set up observatories and launch campaigns.

Trein Tram Bus (TTB) is a Belgian non-profit organisation whose main activity is promoting sustainable mobility, in particular public transport. In interdisciplinary workshops, we developed a citizen observatory on the FLAMENCO platform: a campaign to register cycling routes of Flemish university students, aimed at collecting data on the most popular cycling routes and measuring the satisfaction regarding route safety and quality. A secondary goal of the observatory was to promote cycling among students. The workshops were attended by representatives of TTB as well as of research groups VUB-MOBI (urban mobility), VUB-SMIT (communication sciences) and VUB-SOFT (software development). The campaign was called “Goe Gefietst”, which means both well done and well cycled in Flemish. The co-creation process started in July 2018 and was meant to last 1 year, with a final campaign in April/May 2019. In July 2018 the requirements were discussed, based on the previously set-up guidelines. In October 2018, the application was created in the platform while the set-up process was monitored and observed. After making the necessary internal tests and adjustments, the first external test of the data collection campaign took place in November 2018. Unfortunately, because of reorganisations within TTB, the final campaign (a data collection of two weeks) has been cancelled and will be replaced by a different campaign with another NGO.

3.1. Four-step approach

The first tests of the campaign can already be used to learn valuable lessons on the validation of the technical framework and the FLAMENCO platform itself. The campaign has been created and evaluated in four main steps. In the first step, we define the requirements applied to this specific use case. Secondly, the observatory is created, and we observe the level of guidance needed during the creation. The third phase consists of the 5-day testing period of the citizen observatory campaign through which data is collected. Finally, we evaluate whether the citizen observatory gives the desired results in terms of accuracy and user experience.

STEP 1: Using interviews and co-creation workshops, we matched the technical requirements covered in the

theoretical framework with the specific needs and objectives of this campaign. Table 1 shows an overview of the meetings held. During this process, we evaluated the completeness of the framework. The first step includes defining all possible aspects of the campaign. Among these are: main objectives, sampling strategy, data to be collected, sensors to be used, trade-off between user burden and accuracy and battery drain, level of processing, indicators and algorithms, visualization of output and timing.

Table 1. Overview of interviews and interdisciplinary workshops with TTB

Date	Subject	# Attendees
12 July 2018	Define main objective and requirements	6
27 August 2018	Ongoing developments, planning	5
3 October 2018	Creation workshop	8
17 October 2018	Evaluation of motivation and representativeness	5
26 October 2018	Evaluation parameters and recruiting participants	5
7 December 2018	Evaluation of campaign	13

STEP 2: The creation of the smartphone application and campaign dashboard took place in an interdisciplinary cocreation workshop, together with 8 people (3 campaign organisers of TTB, 4 researchers and one software developer familiar with the platform). Observing the creation process allows us to evaluate this campaign creation.

STEP 3: After creation, the application has been tested internally and mistakes were corrected. These steps need to be repeated until the test version is approved. Only when the test version is approved, the final campaign (or in this case the external test) can start. The campaign took place in a 5-day period from 12-16 November 2018. The application was downloaded and used by 14 participants.

STEP 4: After the campaign took place, we can fully evaluate the functionality of the citizen observatory. The evaluation is two-fold: the user experience as well as technical requirements need to be measured. In this paper, we focus on the latter. The data collected by the campaign needs to be of a high enough quality to derive knowledge relevant to policymakers. The aim of this last process is to set a standard for evaluating citizen science projects in the mobility domain, where technical requirements with relation to data accuracy, algorithms for indicators, representativeness and reliability can be evaluated in the context of an acceptable rate of battery drain. Since we did not have ground truth data available, we used an exit survey (N=10). Only 2 participants were willing to participate in a focus group interview, therefore this method was not possible, and the focus group was cancelled.

4. Validation under real life conditions

Creating and evaluating a real citizen observatory campaign allows us to test the theoretically drawn up technical framework under real life conditions. During the campaign creation experiment, we observe the guidance needed when using the FLAMENCO platform. Finally, we evaluate whether the data collected through this citizen observatory is accurate and reliable.

4.1. Requirements for “Goe Gefietst” campaign

In the first step we define the different aspects and requirements of the citizen observatory. The requirements were pre-defined by the campaign organizers. First, we looked at the general objectives and constraints for data collection, because they set the tone for further decisions on desired accuracy, user burden and battery depletion. The main objective of the campaign is two-fold: register cycling routes to inform local policy makers about the preferred routes and the perceived safety while cycling, and secondly, to motivate students to cycle more. There are three main constraints in the first external test campaign: the data collection is limited to Brussels (location constraint), lasts for 5 days (time constraint) and is targeted at students of universities located in Brussels (population constraint). The smartphone application to collect the data should be made available on both Android and Apple to not exclude any participants. No requirements could be set concerning the devices because of insufficient knowledge.

After defining the data constraints, we look at raw or calculated data types that should be collected through the observatory in the mobility domain. Raw data collected by smartphone sensors should be time, GPS location and

movement, to calculate the cycled routes. The perceived safety and quality of the cycled route and personal information of the user such as gender, age, school and car ownership should be obtained directly from the user. Weather data should be included from a third-party database. The sensor data needs to be processed into unimodal tracking, with automatic start/stop detection at origin and destination. The observatory should only track cycling, translating to speeds within a certain threshold. To minimize battery depletion, the application should run in the background as much as possible and make use of additional sensors to the GPS sensor. Stops e.g. at traffic lights should also be recorded automatically. The processed data should be lifted to indicators that are useful for the participants to increase their motivation. These includes calories burnt and CO₂-emissions saved, which should be visible in the application. The algorithms to calculate these should be as simple as possible, requiring no additional information from the users. On the campaign dashboard, feedback both to participants and campaign organizers should be provided. The desired visualizations are: cycled trips displayed on a map, traveled distances per unit of time (hour/day/week) and a comparison of travel time and distance with previous units of time. Each user should have its own personal dashboard accessible with a personal login. To campaign organizers, general heat maps displaying all the trips should be generated from the collected data. Also, aggregated data must be exportable to spreadsheet to make further calculations if necessary.

4.2. App creation

In one workshop, three ICT agnostic campaign organizers attempted to create their own citizen observatory, based on the requirements that were set with the help of the theoretical framework. In this stage of the evaluation we try to find out if stakeholders with little or no experience in (smartphone based) transport surveys can set up their own data collection campaign. Quite early in the workshop it became clear that it was too difficult to create an application independently through the platform, and therefore the software developer (VUB-SOFT) continued with a hands-on tutorial of building the observatory. A new citizen observatory and a new campaign within that observatory, together with intake surveys, a smartphone application and a feedback dashboard, can be created online on the FLAMENCO website[†].

During the creation phase, it appeared that a lot of functionalities of the “Goe Gefietst” campaign had not yet been given enough thought. Next to an overestimation of the knowledge of the campaign organizers, the FLAMENCO platform itself also showed some important deficits. With relation to data collection, it was first unclear to the campaign organizers which components of data-collection are only accessible when the participant is online. More information about online and offline data collection and the application running in the background should be provided (to make informed decisions about the battery drain-accuracy trade-off).

When it comes to data processing, several issues popped up: firstly, automatic start/stop detection was not available in the platform. Therefore, the participants need to manually start and end a trip, which increases user burden. The application could not remove outliers due to a weak GPS signal, resulting in unreliable measurements of location and speed. A built-in security check to detect fraud could not be added. This is important if there is a competition or gamification element. If a participant moves at a speed of e.g. 70 km/hr, there is no possibility that that person is cycling. Furthermore, no in-app prompts or notifications could be included and direct input from participants during the campaign was not yet foreseen. Participants need to be able to rate the trip quality after each trip and give feedback about the perceived safety and the environment when a trip is ended. Pre-formulated disclaimers and texts related to user consent were also not yet available. Lastly, no third-party data could be integrated, and no external devices could be connected. A last important limitation is that the feedback feature was not yet present at the day of the workshop.

Because of the limitations of the platform, it was impossible to develop the full working application and online dashboard in the workshop. The software developers from VUB-SOFT therefore adjusted the campaign themselves. In this way, well-functioning data collection during the five-days campaign could be ensured.

4.3. Data collection campaign

Participants have been recruited by TTB through flyers, e-mail and social media. Approximately 200 people were reached and 14 participants entered in the campaign and filled in the intake survey. Figure 3 shows three screenshots taken during this campaign. In the first screenshot the participant sees the live tracking on a map when

[†] www.flamenco.vlaanderen

they are cycling. The screen shows the current speed, distance and calorie-intake during that trip. The second screenshot shows the trip rating, where the participant is required to provide additional information after they indicated to have ended a trip. A 1 to 5-star rating for safety, attractiveness of the environment and quality of the road surface was asked. In this trip rating, the participant was given the opportunity to fill in any remarks about the trip. In the third screen, the participant could consult a summary of the collected information. For privacy reasons, the participants could remove their trips at any given time.

Fig. 3 Screenshots of the “Goe Gefietst” data collection campaign

The feedback to campaign organisers had been made available through an online dashboard, accessible through the FLAMENCO website. The dashboard shows the total distance cycled per user name and per faculty. Additionally, the cycled routes were shown on a map, and the following information about the data collection devices could be retrieved for each trip: device manufacturer, device model, device operating system (Android or iOS), battery percentage when starting the trip and battery percentage when ending the trip. This information was derived directly from the devices and required no additional input from the participants.

4.4. Evaluation

After the campaign ended, we tried to evaluate both the technical as the motivational aspects of the campaign. In an online exit-survey (N=10), participants were asked about their experience with the application and the campaign. Because of the low response rate, the results are only explorative. The participants experienced several technical issues: some trips were not or only partially recorded, speeds were not always correct, and the average speed was not shown. The distance cycled (1st screen), the map showing the cycled route in real-time (1st screen) and the overview of all the cycled trips (3rd screen) were voted most useful by the participants. Respondents stated that they were most likely to participate in a long-term data collection campaign when they are shown how the collected data contributes to a better cycling environment. They were less interested in financial rewards and notifications.

We evaluated whether all the separate technical requirements that were set in the first interview with TTB in July 2018 were met at the end of the campaign, in November 2018. We could state that 28% of the requirements were fully met and a further 20% have been partially met. The evaluation of the accuracy and reliability of the unimodal tracking (recording of trips, speed, distance etc.) was more difficult, because an evaluation framework had not been set up beforehand.

5. Conclusion

The aim of this paper is to evaluate whether stakeholders with little or no experience in (smartphone based) transport surveys can set up their own campaigns in a citizen observatory and collect useful data. By developing a real-life campaign in the framework of the recently developed FLAMENCO platform, we were able to test how technical requirements derived from literature corresponds with a realistic use case. This test occurred in four steps. Although the level of participation in the campaign was rather low, the results presented in this paper do not focus on the data that was collected during the campaign but rather how to design, implement and evaluate a citizen observatory campaign.

In a first step, all relevant requirements of the campaign were defined. The non-profit organisation Trein Tram Bus (TTB), who were the campaign organisers, had a good overview of the general objectives of the campaign (unimodal tracking of cycling and motivating students to cycle more) and knew what to measure, but they were not aware of the current limitations of a campaign. Specific setup guidelines applicable to this type of campaign need to be developed, where all the different data types and feedback options are covered. Additionally, the campaign organisers need to be made aware of the safety issues that come with real-time validation and user input in a data collection campaign that tracks cycling or driving.

The second step occurs during the actual creation of the campaign application and website in an interdisciplinary workshop. At the current stage of the FLAMENCO platform, it appeared to be difficult for the campaign organizers to independently create a first test version of their application through the platform. Help from the software developers in all parts of the process was needed. The inability of the campaign organizers to set up an application was caused by both the limited functionalities of the platform as well as the overestimation of the level of technical knowledge of the campaign organizers by the software developers. This, in turn, made the platform not sufficiently user friendly. More guidance for campaign organizers is therefore needed in the form of manuals, audio-visual aids and hands-on training.

In the third step, the actual campaign was tested during a data collection period of five days. One of the main issues was that the number of participants (10 participants finished the campaign) was very low compared to the initial target of 50-100. Although monitoring the participation during the campaign is necessary, more emphasis on the recruitment phase, occurring before the actual campaign, should be placed. Even with the help of flyers and social media it appeared difficult to reach enough people to have a higher number of participants. More information about recruiting and realistic samples should be provided to the campaign organisers.

Lastly, we evaluated the results in terms of technical requirements and user experience. There were two main impediments for this last step. The first impediment is that the number of participants was too low to draw valid conclusions from the exit-survey. Secondly, an evaluation framework needs to be set up in advance, to evaluate the accuracy and reliability of the collected tracking data and indicators (such as the recording of trips, speeds and distances), and guidelines about how to obtain ground truth data to compare the collected data with.

The results of creating and evaluating the use case through the FLAMENCO platform will serve as a basis for a comprehensive manual that will later be developed. Additionally, other ways of tutoring will be developed, such as hand on training sessions and audio-visual knowledge transfer. An evaluation framework will be created as well as guidelines on representativeness, data accuracy and user motivation. A second phase of the iterative 4-step approach will enable us to further define these guidelines and manuals.

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